

TechOceanS Milestone 8 - TRL7 achieved (Month 48)

Work Packages: 13, 14, 15 and 16

Lead: NOC

Due: 30/09/2024

The minimum TRL of each technology as listed in the DoA Table 1.1 has been achieved. For the RoCSI eDNA sampler this has been exceeded (this is TRL7). The results of this analysis are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1 TechOceanS technologies TRL assessment M48

Technology	TechOceanS TRL transition activity (from DoA)	Notes on TRL progress	TRL assessment
eDNA sampler (RoCSI)	Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator	<p>M8 report: Two solutions were proposed as TechOceanS lessons learned. Mechanical and software developments for RoCSI will increase robustness for automated 'mission-like' operations. Software upgrades were successful in the Icelandic Basin in September in a follow-on project. The team has acquired funding to test the mechanical upgrades under simulated real-world conditions (i.e. currents and movement) before the next deployment.</p> <p><i>M7 report: The RoCSI sampler has now completed multiple science missions both at surface (ships underway systems, mooring, towed behind an ASV) and at depth (Autosubs). It has been licensed for commercial production (McLane Research Laboratories Inc. USA)</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: The pressure maintaining system has proved robust and of reasonable cost and is maintained. The alignment of injectors with cartridges</i></p>	8

		<i>has been developed to be more robust. The device has been tested in simulated (pressure pot) environment and has completed at sea missions</i>	
eDNA sampler (pressure balanced)	As above	<p>M8 report: Following planned stage gate review in WP8 decision was to continue with RoCSI (above) as the project's principle eDNA sampler. Consequently, pressure balanced sampler was re-tasked as microplastics sampler (below).</p> <p><i>M7 report: The pressure balanced sampler has been tested with environmental samples (Empress dock) and evaluated for sample carry over. Carry over performance and sample capacity is at least as good as RoCSI (above)</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: A new pressure-balanced, lower cost and more compact concept has been developed. A benchtop prototype has been constructed and tested vs synthetic samples. Components have been tested in simulated environments (pressure pot)</i></p>	6
Microplastics Sampler	Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator	<p>M8 report: Technology re-tasked from pressure balanced eDNA sampler (above). A complete system capable of autonomous running has been created with all hardware and software completing operational checks. The system has been mounted in rugged enclosure and placed in a representative environment. TRL raised in this reporting period</p> <p><i>M7 report: No further testing has been done with microplastics since M5 but the same system has been demonstrated for eDNA / microorganism sampling with environmental samples as above.</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: An adaptation of the pressure balanced sampler (above) has been evaluated for large volume (100 L) and microplastic samples. Options for throughput increase and microplastic contamination decrease have been developed.</i></p>	6/7

<p>In situ nucleic acid sensor</p>	<p>Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator</p>	<p>M8 report: No further TRL progression has been achieved on the basis that the decision was made to focus on the development of the underlying technologies and techniques in favour of pushing for TRL progression before the technologies were ready. Designs have been updated and fabrication methods have been improved in terms of speed and reliability. Custom tooling has been made to improve fabrication rates. The principal technologies have undergone the most rigorous testing to-date including on location in two field trials at partner institutions SZN (Naples, Italy) and IMBB (Crete, Greece); both occurring in summer 2024.</p> <p><i>M7 report: An end-to-end operation of the complete system (sampling, lysis, NA purification and concentration, amplification, detection) has not been completed. However, each of the modules to achieve these functions has been tested and proven on environment samples. All systems are compatible with in situ deployment and with each other.</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: New molecular assays and techniques have been developed. Each element of the multistage assay has been prototyped. A new fluid format has been developed and this prototyped and tested in the laboratory. Components (reagent chambers) have been tested and performance verified in simulated environments</i></p>	<p>5/6</p>
<p>Imaging Workflow</p>	<p>Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator</p>	<p>M8 report: The workflow and hard-ware for low-bandwidth comms and data compression has been demonstrated in real-world environments using BioCAM on ALR and also Smarty200, at Plocan and at Studland Bay (UK) seagrass (EOV) marine protected area. The system functioned, demonstrating performance on different hardware and Environments.</p> <p><i>M7 report: The image library generation technique has been demonstrated. Least squares objective function was used to minimise difference between the rendered images and training data had an average error of 10.58% for the Praunus Flexuosus data and 10.82% of the shrimp data. Renderings under different illumination settings were generated and validated demonstrating the ability to synthetically generate a large number of gold standard training</i></p>	<p>6</p>

		<p><i>images for training pelagic classifiers. AI and data compression tools have been demonstrated (together with hardware, see below)</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: A new 3D object scanning system and image library generation technique has been developed and image classification algorithms advanced. AI and data compression tools have been developed.</i></p>	
Imaging Hardware	<p>Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator</p>	<p>M8 report: The workflow and hard-ware for low-bandwidth comms and data compression has been demonstrated in real-world environments using BioCAM on ALR and also Smarty200, at Plocan and at Studland Bay (UK) seagrass (EOV) marine protected area. The system functioned, demonstrating performance on different hardware and Environments.</p> <p><i>M7 report: The workflow and hard-ware for low-bandwidth comms and data compression has been demonstrated in real-world environments using BioCAM and also Smarty200, a 1.8m hover capable AUV owned and operated by the University of Southampton the latter at Studland Bay (UK) seagrass (EOV) marine protected area. A functional bench prototype of the UVP6m was developed, but its current performance is unsatisfactory. Further work is needed to understand the differences between the beam simulation and its actual implementation, in order to improve or re-design the optical system and satisfy the specifications.</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: low-bandwidth communication protocols and data compression hardware have been developed for BioCAM. New UVP6 interface specifications and lighting system have been adjusted and characterised through modelling and testing</i></p>	6
Optical PhytoPP sensor (MicroSTAF)	<p>Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator</p>	<p>M8 report: MicroSTAF has been through successful power testing on a SeaGlider and Autonaut (PLOCAN). The inrush current has been decreased from 1.6 A to 0.8 A to extend the range of potential platforms. Updated optical components were designed with the aim of decreasing filter breakthrough to improve data quality in extreme oligotrophic conditions. Initial tests with pre-production parts indicate that the new design has decreased breakthrough by</p>	7

		<p>95%. Software development has progressed well, and a new protocol feature (Ambient Light Start) has been implemented to allow for a shorter cycle time (seen as being particularly important for SeaGlider deployments). CTL is aiming to provide end users with production MicroSTAF systems by March 2025.</p> <p><i>M7 report: We are on target to provide three MicroSTAF systems for field testing in March 2024 and hardware for integration with the AutoSub and Autonaut platforms by December 2023. The MicroSTAF mechanical and optical design are close to being complete. The electronics design has been benchtop tested and is also close to being complete. The software required to provide real time data analysis and system setup has been tested on two cruises: DY149 (RSS Discovery, March 2022) and M178 (Meteor, January 2023).</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: A design with reduced size and power has been developed and components tested. Existing designs (LabSTAF, AutoSTAF) have delivered data for science or in simulated tests.</i></p>	
Bio-assay sensor	Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator	<p>M8 report: All stages of operation enhanced. Multiple samples from the environment can be collected and preconcentrated on to resin cartridges through developed autonomous and programmable equipment. Recovery efficiency has been investigated for several pollution targets. The flexible fluidics for processing samples have been constructed using material from developed bioassays that now use a single fluorescence labelled antibody, instead of the previous two antibodies that were required each time. Longevity studies have shown bioassay material remaining viable for 6+ months. Detection equipment now includes a fluorescence camera option as well as the previous high sensitivity detector.</p> <p><i>M7 report: Antibody-based bioassays have been validated and tested using environmental samples. Integral components of the finished prototype were tested and optimised, from pre-concentration, sample/liquid handling, fluorescence detection and incorporation of reagents (antibodies, contaminant conjugates and liquid) onto the microfluidic device. Manual intervention is still required at some steps during the process, however, electronic and mechanical</i></p>	5

		<p><i>manipulation steps have been introduced, and all modules have been developed specifically for underwater detection.</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: New bio-assays and sample handling systems have been developed. Both a Lab on a disc and new pressure balanced in situ microfluidic format have been developed with components tested in the laboratory and in simulated environments</i></p>	
Biogeochemical sensors	Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator	<p>M8 report: The TADIC sensor was successfully deployed on the AutoSub in Gran Canaria operating and recording data over the full six days on its Southern Mission. On its return the TADIC sensor was serviced and re-calibrated and was successfully deployed on a four-day dock deployment at the National Oceanography Centre in Southampton. The precision and accuracy were much improved from the previous AutoSub deployment and TRL7 requirements were met by its mechanical and hardware performance. However, the analytical performance remained at TRL6 and further work and effort is now being made into moving this forward to TRL7.</p> <p>The two dual nutrient sensors were successfully integrated and deployed on the AutoSub in Gran Canaria. The nitrate and phosphate sensor worked reliably, producing a good dataset with reference and CRM measurements, placing the sensor at TRL7. The silicate and phosphate sensor worked mechanically and in terms of platform integration but suffered from poor chemistry performance. We have since been working on this in the lab and have made good progress. A further dock deployment is anticipated soon, which will take the sensor to TRL7 as planned, but it is currently at TRL6.</p> <p><i>M7 report: A new prototype with latching on chip valves has been tested in the laboratory producing a good calibration. A prototype with new pumps has been demonstrated in the laboratory and simulated environments for nitrate detection and performed well. Three new prototypes for combined i) Nitrate-</i></p>	6/7

		<p><i>Phosphate; ii) Phosphate-Silicate; and iii) Total Alkalinity-Dissolved Inorganic Carbon have been constructed, laboratory tested and i) & iii) tested in the environment (Empress Dock).</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: New concepts for improved valves, pumps and time optimised analysis have been developed and tested in the laboratory and simulated environments</i></p>	
Microcytometer	<p>Integrated sensors / end to end systems validated / demonstrated in an operational environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator</p>	<p>M8 report: A full in situ device has been successfully deployed at a depth of 40m in the bay of Naples in June 2024. A shallow water version had been also deployed from the dock in Taliarte, Gran Canaria. Simultaneous detection of impedance and fluorescence has been demonstrated and the ability to detect and distinguish phytoplankton species.</p> <p><i>M7 report: A full in situ prototype has been constructed and tested in the lab and on environmental samples at atmospheric pressure. A low pressure (10 m depth rating) housing is being used for testing with a 2000+ m depth rated housing made in Titanium designed and currently in manufacture. Simultaneous detection of particle impedance and fluorescence has been demonstrated and used to enumerate and classify (taxonomy) phytoplankton species, as well as discriminate phytoplankton from microplastics.</i></p> <p><i>M5 report: A new in situ design has been developed and optics and impedance detection proven in the laboratory with cultures and particles. A pressure tolerant design has been developed and components tested.</i></p>	6/7

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